

Unravelling the mysteries of arsenic in the Zenne River (Belgium): sources, distribution, geochemistry, and bioavailability

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The Zenne River is a small urban river that originates in the Walloon part of Belgium and crosses the densely populated city of Brussels and industrial area downstream of Brussels. Although the river may seem average in terms of its length (105 km) and basin coverage (1160 km²), it represents a unique ecosystem which attracts attention in terms of its environmental status. Before 2000, most of the sewage generated by the population in the basin was discharged into the river without any treatment. Although the water quality of the Zenne has significantly improved in the last decades due to large investments in sewage water treatment, arsenic (As) concentrations remained unchanged and peaking concentrations were repeatedly reported by researchers in the past. However, no source of As pollution was ever found and thus the elevated concentrations of this toxic metalloid in the river remained an unsolved mystery.

For this reason, we aimed to: (i) assess the longitudinal profile of dissolved and particulate As distribution in river water; (ii) evaluate temporal changes of As in tidal section of the river; (iii) assess As potential bioavailability using the Diffusive Gradients in Thin films (DGT) technique; (iv) investigate the geochemical behaviour of As in sediments; (v) identify the potential sources of As pollution.

To put the puzzle pieces together, we evaluated the results from various monitoring campaigns between 2010 and 2021 where the active and passive sampling of water and sediments was combined. Moreover, to assess the historical trends of water quality regarding As concentrations, and emission inventories, the data from Flemish Environmental Agency (Vlaamse Milieu Maatschappij – VMM) were evaluated.

Our study shows that the concentrations of As in water and sediments sharply increase in the downstream part of the Zenne River and reveals the pattern of large temporal variability caused by the tidal influence. The geochemistry of As in sediments is governed by reductive mobilization of Mn and Fe oxyhydroxides but only small portion (7–34%) of dissolved As present in sediments porewater is labile as determined by the DGT technique. The calculated benthic flux accounts for less than 1% of the input to the river. However, we were able to identify the point source of As located in the small tributary Tangebeek. Although this stream contributes to the Zenne water discharge by 5%, it brings 87% of the As load carried by the Zenne.